

A Study on Customers Perception of E-Banking Services Offered by Private Sector Banks and Public Sector Banks in Sathankulam Taluk

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A.Maria Selvi Jeya

*Assistant Professor in Department of Commerce
M.S.U Constituent College of Arts & Science, Sathankulam*

Abstract

Informational technology in the form of e-banking plays a significant role in providing better services at lower cost. Several innovative IT based services such as Automated Teller Machine (ATM), Internet banking, Smart Cards, Credit Cards, Mobile banking, Phone banking, Anywhere-Anytime banking have provided number of convenient services to the customer. This study is carried out with a need to understand the customers using E-banking services in both private and public sector banks in Sathankulam Taluk. The study is restricted to the Sathankulam Taluk, to the public sector banks and private sector banks e-banking customers. The sampling method adopted in this study for selecting the respondents falls under non probability convenient sampling. The study has been conducted in Sathankulam Taluk. It is found that e-banking offers sufficient service resources and rapidly retrieve the information are the important perception towards responsiveness of e-banking services among the customers of public sector banks and e-banking offers sufficient service resources and employees give prompt service are the important perception towards responsiveness of e-banking services among the customers of private sector banks.

Keywords: E-banking, Responsiveness, Reliability and Perception.

Introduction

Informational technology in the form of e-banking plays a significant role in providing better services at lower cost. Several innovative IT based services such as Automated Teller Machine (ATM), Internet banking, Smart Cards, Credit Cards, Mobile banking, Phone banking, Anywhere-Anytime banking have provided number of convenient services to the customer. The banks which are providing these services on a wider scale to customers are more reputed in the eyes of customers. But at the same time technology based product is different in public and private sector banks.

Need and Scope of the Study

This study is carried out with a need to understand the customers using E-banking services in both private and public sector banks in Sathankulam Taluk. The study is restricted to the Sathankulam Taluk, to the public sector banks and private sector banks e-banking customers.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the customers perception of efficiency of e-banking services privacy/security of e-banking services offered by private sector banks and public sector banks.
- To study the customers perception of reliability of e-banking services and responsiveness of e-banking services offered by private sector banks and public sector banks.

Sampling Design

The sampling method adopted in this study for selecting the respondents falls under non probability convenient sampling. The study has been conducted in Sathankulam Taluk. The findings from the study can be generalized to the whole country as it is not manual banking method that may vary between states but e-banking practices that may be practiced within any part of the country. Well structured questionnaires were circulated to 50 customers of private sector banks and 50 customers of public sector banks. Hence the sample size chosen for the study is 100.

Analysis and Interpretation**Perception of customers in Efficiency of e-banking services**

In order to find out the significant difference in perception of customers towards efficiency of e-banking services of private sector banks and public sector banks in Sathankulam Taluk, 't' test is attempted with the null hypothesis as, "**There is no significant difference in perception of customers towards efficiency of e-banking services of private sector banks and public sector banks in Sathankulam Taluk**". The result of 't' test is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Perception of customers in Efficiency of e-banking services

Sl. No.	Efficiency of e-banking services	Type of Banks (Mean Score)		t Statistics
		Public Sector Banks	Private Sector Banks	
1.	e-banking offers abundant financial services information	4.3729	4.0698	2.853*
2.	Using e-banking is not time consuming	4.2045	3.7907	2.831*
3.	Completing transactions through e-banking is fast and easy	4.1148	3.6667	2.923*
4.	Easily find information from e-banking	4.0000	3.8049	1.480
5.	e-banking offers multimedia functions	3.7085	3.4651	2.417*

Source: Primary data

*-Significant at five per cent level

Table 1 shows that e-banking offers abundant financial services information and using e-banking is not time consuming are the important perception towards efficiency of e-banking services among the customers of public sector banks as their mean scores are 4.3729 and 4.2045 respectively. Table further shows that e-banking offers abundant financial services information and easily find information from e-banking are the important perception towards efficiency of e-banking services among the customers of private sector banks as their mean scores are 4.0698 and 3.8049 respectively. Regarding the perception towards efficiency of e-banking services, e-banking offers

abundant financial services information, using e-banking is not time consuming, completing transactions through e-banking is fast and easy and e-banking offers multimedia functions are statistically significant at 5 per cent level.

Perception of Customers in Privacy/Security of e-Banking Services

In order to find out the significant difference in perception of customers towards privacy/security of e-banking services of private sector banks and public sector banks in Sathankulam Taluk, ‘t’ test is attempted with the null hypothesis as, **“There is no significant difference in perception of customers towards privacy/security of e-banking services of private sector banks and public sector banks in Sathankulam Taluk”**. The result of ‘t’ test is presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Perception of Customers in Privacy/Security of e-banking Services

Sl. No.	Privacy/Security of e-banking services	Type of Banks (Mean Score)		t Statistics
		Public Sector Banks	Private Sector Banks	
1	Making transactions through e-banking is safe	3.8152	3.9871	1.723
2	E-banking protects privacy and transaction information	3.5571	3.3928	1.705
3	E-banking has basic safety protection functions	3.5308	3.3679	1.426
4	E-banking has clear transaction safety policies	3.5915	3.7560	1.418
5	Feel safe in e-banking transactions	3.6274	3.3085	3.171*
6	Secure in providing sensitive information (e.g. credit card number) for e-banking transactions	3.3365	3.4533	1.210
7	Feel the risk associated with e-banking transactions is low	3.3934	3.3757	0.175

Source: Primary data

*-Significant at five per cent level

It is understood from table 2 that making transactions through e-banking is safe and feel safe in e-banking transactions are the important perception towards privacy/security of e-banking services among the customers of public sector banks as their mean scores are 3.8152 and 3.6274 respectively. Table further shows that making transactions through e-banking is safe and e-banking has clear transaction safety policies are the important perception towards privacy/security of e-banking services among the customers of private sector banks as their mean scores are 3.9871 and 3.7560 respectively. Regarding the perception towards privacy/security of e-banking services, feel safe in e-banking transactions is statistically significant at 5 per cent level.

Perception in Reliability of e-Banking Services

In order to find out the significant difference in perception of customers towards reliability of e-banking services of private sector banks and public sector banks in Sathankulam Taluk, ‘t’ test

is attempted with the null hypothesis as, “**There is no significant difference in perception of customers towards reliability of e-banking services of private sector banks and public sector banks in Sathankulam Taluk**”. The result of ‘t’ test is presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Perception of Customers in Reliability of e-banking Services

Sl. No.	Reliability of e-banking services	Type of Banks (Mean Score)		t Statistics
		Public Sector Banks	Private Sector Banks	
1	Termination during a transaction does not happen in e-banking	3.9545	4.1198	1.452
2	The transaction processing system of e-banking is error free	3.8308	3.5485	2.573*
3	E-banking offers 24/7 services	4.2481	4.5582	2.510*
4	E-banking performs services truly and reliably	3.3018	3.5840	2.317*
5	Performs the service correctly	3.7237	4.1042	2.781*
6	E-banking keeps records accurately	3.5688	3.8865	2.479*

Source: Primary data

*-Significant at five per cent level

It is understood from table 3 that e-banking offers 24/7 services and termination during a transaction does not happen in e-banking are the important perception towards reliability of e-banking services among the customers of public sector banks as their mean scores are 4.2481 and 3.9545 respectively. Table further shows that e-banking offers 24/7 services and termination during a transaction does not happen in e-banking are the important perception towards reliability of e-banking services among the customers of private sector banks as their mean scores are 4.5582 and 4.1198 respectively. Regarding the perception towards reliability of e-banking services, the transaction processing system of e-banking is error free, e-banking offers 24/7 services, e-banking performs services truly and reliably, performs the service correctly and e-banking keeps records accurately are statistically significant at 5 per cent level.

Perception in Responsiveness of e-Banking Services

In order to find out the significant difference in perception of customers towards responsiveness of e-banking services of private sector banks and public sector banks in Sathankulam Taluk, ‘t’ test is attempted with the null hypothesis as, “**There is no significant difference in perception of customers towards responsiveness of e-banking services of private sector banks and public sector banks in Sathankulam Taluk**”. The result of ‘t’ test is presented in Table 4.

Table 4 Perception of Customers in Responsiveness of e-Banking Services

Sl. No.	Reliability of e-banking services	Type of Banks (Mean Score)		t Statistics
		Public Sector Banks	Private Sector Banks	
1	Termination during a transaction does not happen in e-banking	3.9545	4.1198	1.452
2	The transaction processing system of e-banking is error free	3.8308	3.5485	2.573*

3	E-banking offers 24/7 services	4.2481	4.5582	2.510*
4	E-banking performs services truly and reliably	3.3018	3.5840	2.317*
5	Performs the service correctly	3.7237	4.1042	2.781*
6	E-banking keeps records accurately	3.5688	3.8865	2.479*

Source: Primary data

*-Significant at five per cent level

Table 4 shows that e-banking offers sufficient service resources and rapidly retrieve the information are the important perception towards responsiveness of e-banking services among the customers of public sector banks as their mean scores are 3.7795 and 3.6243 respectively. Table further shows that e-banking offers sufficient service resources and employees give prompt service are the important perception towards responsiveness of e-banking services among the customers of private sector banks as their mean scores are 3.9873 and 3.8975 respectively. Regarding the perception towards responsiveness of e-banking services, employees give prompt service, receive prompt responses to requests by email or other means, quickly resolves problems encountered and promptly informs important information are statistically significant at 5 per cent level.

Suggestions

E-Banking Customers of present days are very broad minded and they have accepted the present e-banking methods easily. Hence the problems are not so high towards Socio cultural in e-banking services. However there is slight dissatisfaction like customer requirement to have to get printed bills while enjoying e-banking services. The public sector banks and private sector banks must ensure that such mild requirements are fulfilled in order to avoid major dissatisfaction in future.

Conclusion

It is concluded that reliability and responsiveness bring less satisfaction among the customers towards E-banking services offered by the private sector banks and public sector banks in Sathankulam Taluk.

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